

Debromination of Chalcone Dibromide and Stilbene Dibromide with Sodium Hydrogen Sulphide[†]

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Manuscript received 22 May 1985, revised 24 December 1985, accepted 17 February 1986

Sodium hydrogen sulphide debrominated chalcone dibromide and α -bromo- β -hydroxychalcone and also stilbene dibromide in methanol to chalcone and stilbene, respectively.

DEBROMINATION of *vic*-dihaloalkanes and α,β -dibromoketones have been studied by earlier workers using the debrominating agents, like potassium iodide in acetone¹, stannous chloride in different solvents², sodium hydrogen selenide³, thiourea in ethanol^{4,5} and also by some recent workers using hydrated sodium sulphide under phase transfer conditions^{6,7} and photochemical and chemical reduction of *vic*-dihalides *via* phase transfer of 4,4'-bipyridinium radical⁸ for solar energy conversion. Use of cobalt octacarbonyl on alumina has been reported for selective dehalogenation of α -bromosulphoxides⁹. Chromium(II) acetate also brings reductive debromination in *vic*-dihaloalkanes¹⁰ and chalcone dibromides¹¹.

- a, R=CH₃, R'=OCH₃, X=OH, Y=Br.
b, R=X=H, R'=OCH₃, Y=Br.
c, R=R'=X=H, Y=Br.
d, R=CH₃, R'=H, X=OH, Y=Br.
e, R=CH₃, R'=OCH₃, X=OAc, Y=Br.
f, R=CH₃, R'=OCH₃, X=OAc, Y=OH.

Sodium sulphide with *vic*-dibromo derivatives of certain oximes is reported to give sulphoxide derivatives¹². Chalcone with anhydrous sodium sulphide in dry ethanol gives thiophenes and with excess of sodium sulphide in acetyl acetone at room temperature is reported to give PhCOCH₂CSPH¹³. Thiourea with 2'-hydroxychalcones gives 1,3-thiamine derivatives in alkaline ethanol on refluxing

for 3 h while in 10 min in DMSO¹⁴. Sodium polysulphide with chalcones is reported to form 2,4-dibenzoyl-3,5-diphenylthiolanes¹⁵.

Chalcone dibromides (2a-e); α -bromo- β -hydroxychalcone (2f) or stilbene dibromide (*meso*) (0.055 mol) was treated with freshly prepared sodium hydrogen sulphide (0.01 mol) in dry methanol (30 ml). The reaction mixture was heated from 10 min to 1 h and then diluted with water. The product was crystallised from rectified spirit. 2a-d regenerated original chalcone 1a-d; 2e-f gave 2-acetoxy of 1a and stilbene dibromide gave *trans*-stilbene in 80% yield. The crude products on tlc examination gave two spots, one of chalcone and another of sulphur (stilbene and sulphur in case of stilbene dibromide).

Sodium hydrogen sulphide was prepared by saturating sodium ethoxide solution with dry H₂S and precipitating NaSH by adding dry ether. NaSH was filtered at the pump. (NaSH reacts with moisture evolving H₂S very rapidly).

The reductive debromination in the above compounds was an important observation during our study in the synthesis of thioflavonoids.

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[†] Submitted in July '83 for 71st session of Indian Science Congress, 1983, as poster paper.

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